

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

Grant Agreement No 731032

Deliverable Report 10.4

Deliverable	D10.4 - First Testing and Evaluation Results of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan
Work Package	WP10: NA4 – Integration & Sustainability
Delivery date	M36 - 8 th January 2021
Lead Beneficiary	BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (BNN)
Nature of Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)

Submitted by Beatriz Alfaro Serrano, Andreas Falk, Susanne Resch and Johanna Scheper (BNN), Iseult Lynch and Anastasios Papadiamantis (UoB), Thomas Exner, Barry Hardy and Kevin Prudence (EwC), Dieter Maier (Biomax), Egon Willighagen (UM), Socorro Vazquez Campos (LEITAT), Martin Himly (PLUS), Antreas Afantitis (NovaM)

Revised by Lee Walker (UKCEH) and Antreas Afantitis (NovaM)

Approved by Iseult Lynch (UoB)

Summary

Sustainability has become one of the hot topics in the past years. It is a complex, multidisciplinary field that encompasses many different aspects, considering environmental, social and economic factors that shall be taken into account. One crucial aspect of it can be described as “the ability to be maintained at a certain rate or level¹”. For a research infrastructure project like NanoCommons, sustainability means that the services designed and developed during the project will continue to be maintained, and ideally further developed, beyond the end of the funded period of the project, ensuring future accessibility for users and potential customers. The Deliverable 10.4 “First Testing and Evaluation Results of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan” will refer to the economic level of sustainability, unless otherwise specified.

Deliverable 10.4 builds on the previous deliverable D10.3 “Initial version of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan”, adding a first business plan and reflecting additional conceptualisation and operationalisation of the NanoCommons sustainability plan in the second and third year of the project runtime. It includes updates on the evolving landscape and the services that are available. The work done up to M35 of the project runtime is summarized, with references to the corresponding related documents (e.g., deliverables, webpage, etc.) and how this collectively builds towards the main objective of achieving a sustainable and open knowledge infrastructure for the whole nanosafety community. Furthermore, a business concept for NanoCommons has been developed, with the aim to ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes after the project’s end.

¹ www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/sustainability

Table of Contents

Summary	2
Table of Contents	3
List of Abbreviations	4
Terminology	6
1) Introduction	7
Sustainability Concept Approach	8
Sustainable Development Goals	8
Challenges to Sustainability of tools and services developed in EU projects	10
2) Elements of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan	17
NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI)	17
Aim of the NanoCommons KI	17
Content and structure of the NanoCommons KI	17
Access to and business models for the NanoCommons KI	20
Contributors to and Users of the NanoCommons KI	20
Services and Tools	25
Online Training	25
Support Service – Helpdesk	28
Status of activities to implement the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan	28
NanoCommons Case Studies	32
3) Business Concept for NanoCommons	35
NanoCommons Organisation	35
IPR strategy	36
4) NanoCommons Organisation’s Business Plan	37
Financial structure	38
Costs	40
Revenues	41
Balance sheet	42
5) Next steps during the final period of the project	44
6) Conclusions	46
7) References	47
Annexes	48

Annex 1 – Results of the NanoCommons Online Survey	48
Annex 2 – List of Services & Tools provided by the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure	49
Annex 3 – NanoCommons Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	51

List of Abbreviations

API – Application Programming Interface
CS – Case Study
CRO – Contract Research Organisation
DW – Data Warehouse
ENM – Engineered Nanomaterial
EOSC – European Open Science Cloud
EPPN – European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs
ESFRI – European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESPCI – Ecole Supérieure de Physique et Chimie Industrielle de la ville de Paris
ETP – European Technology Platform
ETPN – European Technology Platform in Nanomedicine
EUON – European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials
F2F – Face to Face
FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAQ – Frequently Asked Questions
GA – General Assembly
GD – Guidance Documents
GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
ICS – Industrial Case Study
IPR – Intellectual Property Right
ITN – Innovative Training Network
JRA – Joint Research Activity
KB – Knowledge Base
KER – Key Exploitable Result
KI – Knowledge Infrastructure
KPI – Key Performance Indicator
MSCA – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action
NA – Networking Activity
NBI – Nanomaterial-Biological Interaction
NC – NanoCommons
NM – Nanomaterial
NSC – NanoSafety Cluster
OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
QA – Quality Assurance

RA – Risk Assessment
RI – Research Infrastructure
SDG – Sustainable Development Goals
TA – Transnational Access
TG – Test Guideline
TRL – Technology Readiness Level
TU – Technical University

Short names of the NanoCommons partners referred to throughout this deliverable

BfR – Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
BNN – BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH
DUKE – Duke University
EwC – Edelweiss Connect
LEITAT – Leitat Technological Center (Acondicionamiento Tarrasense Associacion)
MU – Maastricht University
NovaM – NovaMechanics
NTUA – National Technical University of Athens
OREGON – Oregon State University
PLUS – Paris-Lodron-Universität Salzburg
UCD – University College Dublin
UKCEH – United Kingdom Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
UoB – University of Birmingham

Terminology

During the preparation of Deliverable report D10.4, the terminology used within NanoCommons was aligned and defined:

- *NanoCommons Organisation*: a proposed financial entity that could operate the *NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure* following the end of the project (as yet to be established).
- *NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI)*: this is the backbone of the NanoCommons Organisation, including the consultancy and the services, and will include the administrative, business and collaboration aspects of NanoCommons. It is currently mainly delivered via the project webpage and the catalogue of services.
- *NanoCommons Services*: the services listed and described in detail in the NanoCommons KI catalogue of services (note this is continuously expanding).
- *NanoCommons Consultancy*: the consultancy services listed and described in detail in the NanoCommons KI. At present, this expertise / consultancy is delivered in large part through the transnational Access (TA) activities and in a future iteration is the means to provide our expertise to users and the wider community.
- *NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB)* establishes the links to the data sources including the NanoCommons Data Warehouse and provides the user interface and application programming interfaces (APIs) for advanced data visualisation, searching, browsing and accessing features.
- *NanoCommons Data Warehouse (DW)* is part of the NanoCommons KB, containing the data that is made publicly available for the first time (and not just linked to) by NanoCommons.

1) Introduction

The overall objective of the NanoCommons project is to develop the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI) for nanosafety assessment, by integrating a range of data management and nanoinformatics services, as well as building and supporting the user community. It must be attractive for the community of users by *providing solutions* that solve important problems and satisfy the informatics needs of the nanomaterials' safety community. An example of an identified need is that small to medium enterprises (SMEs) have difficulties understanding how they should respond to the emerging complex science and regulations associated with nanosafety. NanoCommons strives to develop services and tools that address those gaps and bring the solutions to potential customers. Therefore, engagement with potential users and/or customers of the NanoCommons' Tools and Services, and co-development of solutions with them, where appropriate, is a central aspect of the project's implementation. In the absence of such an engagement NanoCommons risks to be developed as a concept and a set of resources without real committed users with little realistic chance of survival beyond the funding period. We note that the Covid-19 pandemic has greatly impacted the ability to engage in face-to-face activities with users and stakeholders, but that we have adapted our approaches to online engagement, and to including discussions with the TA users on their experiences of the NanoCommons services and their willingness to pay for such services in the future.

NanoCommons, as a starting e-infrastructure, must excel and exceed the usual expectations. A key focus for the project and especially its sustainability is to offer a **toolbox of services and tools** that SMEs need, use and will be willing to pay for. However, we are not the first, nor will we be the last infrastructure project to grapple with these issues, and as such we have made significant efforts to learn from the experiences of others and from the EU's long-term commitment to infrastructure development and maintenance. One example of this is the ESFRI report on Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures made 7 key recommendations for sustaining large-scale research infrastructures², as follows:

- 1) Establish and maintain excellence through the entire lifecycle of Research Infrastructures (RIs) by all appropriate means, by **securing adequate framework conditions**, and by **opening the RIs up to the world**.
- 2) Ensure that RIs have the right people in the right place at the right time by **strengthening and harmonising national research and educational systems** to make sure that all essential skills are available.
- 3) **Harmonise and integrate a vision for convergent operation of RIs and e-Infrastructures in Europe** to ensure cost-effective service provision to the user communities.
- 4) Fully exploit the potential of RIs as innovation hubs by **incorporating strategies for their development into national and European innovation policies**.
- 5) Set up effective means of **determining the economic and wider social value of RIs**, and incorporate these benefits into science-policy-society dialogues.
- 6) Establish adequate framework conditions for **effective governance and sustainable long-term funding for RIs** at every stage in their lifecycle, together with effective management.

² https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/pdf/esfri/publications/esfri_scripta_vol2.pdf

- 7) **Foster broader coordination** at National and European levels when designing processes for planning and supporting national and pan European RIs enhancing their strategic value.

Key elements of these recommendations were used in designing the NanoCommons sustainability plan which shall make the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI) a long-term asset in the European R&D&I ecosystem. In the initial version of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan defined in the Deliverable D10.3, the goals to be pursued by the JRA and TA activities are presented, including the calls for “micro projects” and how their results and learnings can be utilised to further improve the NanoCommons KI and demonstrate its value for customers.

Deliverable 10.4 presents the concept for the NanoCommons business model, taking into account results and learnings from the initial sustainability plan (D10.3) and the feedback gained from the ongoing Joint Research Activities (JRA) and TAs. Thus, D10.4 will enable the next generation of JRA and TA activities, to be more tailored to service-orientation aspects as it is needed for business cases, and shall include a monitoring of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the developed tools and models and how this improves through integration into the NanoCommons KI. Specifically, the implementation is supported by ongoing case studies, which are used to evaluate the NanoCommons KI in real world settings. Due to the fact that they contain confidential, sensitive and partly personal information, they cannot be shown in the public deliverable, according to confidentiality agreements and/or the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Please note that D10.4 includes references to other deliverables from NanoCommons. Those are either available at the project webpage³, as well as in the NanoCommons Community in Zenodo⁴, or in case of confidentiality issues, excerpts are presented herein.

Sustainability Concept Approach

To date just the economic level of sustainability has been taken into account in the development of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan. By considering the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), aligning our e-infrastructure development to be consistent with these goals, and incorporating ideas on how and where NanoCommons can contribute to the achievement of these goals into our overall sustainability plan, we will achieve a balance between the three main levels of sustainability: economic, environmental and social.

We start here by defining the general sustainability concept along the value chain of a project (infrastructure in the case of NanoCommons) and the alignment of this conceptual approach with pan-European and international Sustainable Development Goals.

Sustainable Development Goals

³ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/news-events/outputs/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/nanocommons/search?page=1&size=20&subtype=deliverable>

The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were set in 2015 by the UN General Assembly⁵ and are intended to be achieved by the year 2030, as per UN Resolution 70/1 setting out the 2030 Agenda⁶. They are a collection of 17 global goals (see Figure 1) designed to be a "blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all"⁷.

The 17 SDGs are interlinked, so that the actions in one area affect the others. Moreover, the main goal of sustainability is to address and balance the following three main pillars (see Figure 2): **economic sustainability** (also referred to as *profit*), **environmental sustainability** (also referred to as *planet*) and **social sustainability** (also referred to as *people*).

Figure 1. Overview of the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

The SDGs present an opportunity for NanoCommons to be developed and implemented in a manner consistent with these goals. Therefore, NanoCommons will provide support in the achievement of these goals through its research support services as those are essential tools for development of safe and sustainable nanomaterials (NMs), which will have a positive impact in the “global innovation system” for sustainable development technologies. In order to contribute towards the SDGs and incorporate the SDGs into our business plan and strategy, our first objective is to map the SDGs onto the NanoCommons value chain to identify which SDGs are the most important for us, as not all 17 SDGs will be equally relevant for NanoCommons. The extent to which NanoCommons can contribute to each, and the risks and opportunities they individually represent, depends on many factors. Taking a strategic approach to the SDGs, our first task is to conduct an assessment on the current, potential, positive and negative impacts that NanoCommons’ business activities have on the SDGs throughout the value chain. This will help to identify where positive impacts can be scaled up and where negative impacts can be reduced or avoided.

⁵ https://www.un.org/ga/search/view_doc.asp?symbol=A/RES/70/1&Lang=E

⁶ <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld>

⁷ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

Figure 2. Identified SDGs in the three pillars of sustainability, which NanoCommons is addressing/planning to address.

Challenges to Sustainability of tools and services developed in EU projects

Difficulties and challenges for achieving economic sustainability of tools and related products are analysed. NanoCommons will identify and integrate lessons learnt from the **GUIDEnano tool** in terms of its progress towards achieving economic sustainability for this tool beyond the initial project lifetime.

Here we consider the challenges of achieving sustainability of tools and products, and therefore provide a guide for ourselves and other projects in dealing with these issues. Below, a brief explanation of how the tools have been constructed in a way to offer sustainability and portability is described, beginning with NanoCommons internal tools and ending with an external tool, the [GUIDEnano tool](#)⁸ for risk assessment of NMs across their life cycle.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the majority of tools/services offered by the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure are developed and owned by NanoCommons project partners. These tools have been developed in order to offer sustainable and portable services. As described in section 2 “Elements of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan”, most of these tools are integrated within the NanoCommons KI and are inter-operable and sustainable as a unit.

The tools and services under development by the NanoCommons partners encompass multiple

⁸ <https://projects.leitat.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/newsletter-2.pdf>

technologies and multiple programming languages. Establishing a single standard approach for software development would be impractical for the project partners and the wider community. Nevertheless, integration of these numerous and diverse services into an interoperable environment requires some form of standardization. Instead of standardizing the underlying technologies, one possible solution will be using a service-based architecture and standardizing the deployment of tools and services by using containerization. Delivery of software components in the form of containers gives the tool developer the freedom to select his/her preferred means for implementing the services (free choice of programming language/ implementation in multiple environments etc.) with limitations only on the provided application programming interface (API). As noted also in NanoCommons Deliverable report D4.2 – Initial APIs “NanoCommons is not proposing a one-size-fits all solution, but rather designing itself to be adaptive and responsive to the breath of APIs and communication approaches already available in the nanoinformatics and chemoinformatics fields. In NanoCommons, this is achieved by defining and constantly refining guidelines for the development and adaptation of APIs, through which the data transfer, parametrization and execution of the services are performed, and which allows for the combination of the services into workflows or the development of graphical user interfaces on top of the services to provide user-friendly access to the tools or models.”

It is also important to note that most cloud vendors, both private and public, offer containerized software support. Choosing development through containers ensures that NanoCommons tools and services will be in line with evolutions in cloud offerings in the next few years while also allowing easy integration into European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructures, for example. The partners' suggestion is to provide their services as docker images, and that these will be deployed to the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure as running containers (see Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. NanoCommons Models and Tools will be implemented as Micro Services in Docker to ensure their sustainability.

Figure 4. NanoCommons Models integrated under a common platform (the NanoCommons KI).

All NanoCommons tools will be accessible via [KNIME](https://www.knime.org/)⁹, a user friendly, open-source data analysis platform with a very strong and active community. A series of NanoCommons KNIME nodes, will be built upon the existing open-source KNIME infrastructure, to significantly increase the number of available nodes dedicated to solving nanosafety and nanoinformatics problems. More specifically, the NanoCommons KNIME toolbox will help to bridge different nanoinformatics and modelling tools upon the same interface and contribute in two directions: (1) the efficient exploitation of NMs datasets available in databases (e.g., the NanoCommons Knowledge Base), and (2) the implementation of images analysis, predictive nanoinformatics and risk assessment models utilising the integrated datasets processed via the NanoCommons KNIME nodes and NanoCommons Knowledge Base.

Containerised NanoCommons tools and services, equipped with APIs, are also accessible from programming notebooks (similar to laboratory notebooks but for computational workflows), such as [Jupyter notebooks](https://jupyter.org/)¹⁰. This option supports further the sustainability of the products of the project, because it provides additional flexibility in interconnecting the NanoCommons tools and integrating them with external services, with the goal of developing custom workflows, according to the specific needs and requirements of the users. In NanoCommons Deliverable D4.6 for example, we have demonstrated that through a Jupyter notebook, a user can create an integrated workflow, which searches and retrieves data from the NanoCommons Knowledge base, applies pre-processing methods like variable selection and scaling, generates a predictive model for a biological endpoint via integration with the [Scikit Learn](https://scikit-learn.org/stable/)¹¹ machine learning library and eventually deploys the model as a user-friendly web service for risk assessment of NMs.

As a starting point for assessing challenges to sustainability and lessons that can be learned from previous partner / project experiences, we carefully examined the *GUIDEnano tool*¹², as although this tool was conceptualised and its development led by a NanoCommons partner (LEITAT) the software and implementation is owned by a company external to NanoCommons. Through discussions with

⁹ www.knime.org

¹⁰ <https://jupyter.org/>

¹¹ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

¹² <https://tool.guidenano.eu/>

both LEITAT and the external party we explored how the tool was developed (which software platform, if and how it communicates with other tools, whether it has or plans to have an API etc.) and which approaches it has taken to sustain and/or further develop itself. In this case, sustaining the tools means keeping the data upon which the GUIDEnano tool runs up to date, continuously expanding the product and release scenarios, and remaining aligned with regulatory processes which for example, in 2019 introduced the concept of nanoforms and sets of nanoforms under the updating of the REACH guidelines for NMs¹³. As concepts such as Safe-by-Design and circular economy become embedded into NMs manufacturing and the production of nano-enabled products, the GUIDEnano tool also needs to expand to capture these processes.

The GUIDEnano tool guides nano-enabled product developers (industry) into the risk assessment process. It was developed within the EU FP7 funded project GUIDEnano between 2013 and 2017. Although the project ended 3 years ago, at the time of this writing this deliverable, the tool developers and the coordinator of the project are managing to further develop the tool and ensure its sustainability via inclusion in subsequent and current European projects (caLIBRAte, NanoCommons, GRACIOUS, SAbyNA), as well as with some internal resources. NanoCommons is one of the projects supporting the onward development of the tool. However, there are significant intellectual property challenges and software access issues that have been thrown-up by the activities to integrate GUIDEnano into NanoCommons, which were discussed in further detail in Deliverable D6.3 (Initial version of the integrated web-based decision support system for regulators) and have required the development of a number of work-around solutions to be developed by NanoCommons partners.

Initial version of the GUIDEnano tool:

The original tool was developed by the GUIDEnano project partner ThinkWorks B.V.¹⁴ by integrating all of the knowledge generated by all other GUIDEnano project partners into a web-based tool.

Once the GUIDEnano project finished in 2017, the GUIDEnano tool v3 was released as the main outcome of the project. ThinkWorks B.V. kept the proprietary rights of the tool but does not own all the knowledge within the tool. The generated knowledge was free to be published by the different partners involved in the different tool development parts (i.e., the characterisation, exposure, release, hazard and risk modules). The available version of the tool is *free* for any user who would like to use it by requesting a password to get access. GUIDEnano included this requirement for a password in order to guide the users through the tool, if requested, and to be able to monitor which types of stakeholders show interest in the tool. The guidance is offered to both better explain the steps to follow into the risk assessment process and to indicate limitations of the current version that might have an impact on the purpose of the risk assessment needed by the individual user. At the end of the project a list of improvements and new knowledge developments were identified with the aim to provide a more user-friendly version of the tool and with more functionalities integrated in the structure. Therefore, future versions were already planned to be realized after the end of the GUIDEnano project.

¹³https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13655/how_to_register_nano_en.pdf/f8c046ec-f60b-4349-492b-e915fd9e3ca0

¹⁴ <http://www.thinkworks.nl/>

Actual status:

Once the project ended, the tool has been further developed using different funding resources (i.e., internal resources (LEITAT) and EU funding activities within other EU projects), as follows:

*caLIBRAte*¹⁵ project selected GUIDEnano as one of the tools for RA to be tested and validated using different case studies. These activities facilitated the identification of potential modifications and further developments needed for the GUIDEnano Tool and it has been reported to the tool owners to be considered in future developments. Some of those modifications were considered and have been integrated in the current version.

Within the *GRACIOUS*¹⁶ project, a framework for grouping of NMs is being developed. The GRACIOUS grouping framework is intended to be easily linked to existing tools and Decision Support Systems. GUIDEnano is considered one of the showcase tools which will integrate this framework in the timeframe of the GRACIOUS project. Furthermore, GUIDEnano is trying to connect with the eNanoMapper database.

Within the *NanoCommons* project, further development of the tool is ongoing: the Activity card library (release rates for different exposure scenarios) will contribute to the user friendliness of the tool. Connection with data included in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base is also being explored. These extensions are not freely available to the community yet, since those changes will need to be validated with different case studies. In the near future, the interoperability of GUIDEnano with other tools through APIs is not being considered by ThinkWorks. As presented in NanoCommons deliverable D6.3, the interoperability is for now only possible indirectly by using the GUIDEnano data output as the data entry for other tools, via a small release scenarios database developed within NanoCommons.

However, the fact that the intellectual property rights of the GUIDEnano tool belong to ThinkWorks B.V., means that further developments on the tool, within the scope of subsequent projects, must be discussed and aligned with them, or open source workarounds must be developed that engage with the free version of GUIDEnano and build upon it. Currently, any changes and the onward development are performed by ThinkWorks. This includes integration of additional knowledge generated during the GUIDEnano project as well as all the knowledge generated in the current projects in which further developments of the GUIDEnano Tool were planned (NanoCommons, GRACIOUS, and SAbYNA). Within NanoCommons, ThinkWorks and LEITAT are working on a mirror version that will be public, when all of the desired updates (i.e., release library and link with the NanoCommons database infrastructure) will be finished and tested. Even if modifications of the code still need to be done by ThinkWorks, integration of additional knowledge is possible.

Further developments:

Different options are being analysed by LEITAT and ThinkWork in order to continue with the next step and evolve GUIDEnano into a *commercial tool*, considering a *basic* and free version and a *premium* one with added value capabilities under a regular fee basis. Currently, further improvements towards

¹⁵ <http://www.nanocalibrate.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://www.h2020gracious.eu/>

a user-friendly version of the tool, as well as improvements in some of the modules, updating them with current knowledge, is the first priority. Within the GRACIOUS project, GUIDEnano will be a showcase of a Risk Assessment tool for the implementation of the Grouping Framework. Within the SAByNA project, funds are dedicated to improve it for safe-by-design purposes. The implementation of updated/ future GUIDEnano versions into the NanoCommons infrastructure platform will need to be discussed in a future stage.

Further developments and maintenance services needed for future versions of GUIDEnano are dependent on the following factors:

1. Software licences (third party software used)
2. Technical maintenance (keeping the tool running, like adapting the tool to browser, server and security updates etc.)
3. Support (granting access, answering questions, etc.)
4. Content maintenance (updating existing rules based on changes in regulations, new insights)
5. Extending the tool with new knowledge/modules functionalities
6. Communication, management, etc.

The costs to cover these factors is large and could range anywhere between 15 to 150 kEuro annually, depending on whether the owners opt to just 'keep the tool afloat for scientific purposes' or 'improve/extend and actively professionalize' the tool for wide industrial usage.

Lessons learnt for improved sustainability:

The NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI) rests on the idea of facilitating the linking of data with tools and integrating the offers of different providers. Therefore, the value of the infrastructure is dependent on the services offered through it. Exploitation and sustainability activities have to take into account that IPR may be linked to the developer of a tool (its creator/owner) where open approaches and open licences are not used, and this will certainly guide future decisions in terms of where to focus our activity in terms of integrating tools and services.

At the moment, most of the tools being offered by the KI are owned by partners in the NanoCommons consortium but these cannot cover all relevant areas of nanosafety research. The GUIDEnano tool is the first prominent example, where a community need is currently served by a tool owned by a non-NanoCommons partner. To get such third-party tools integrated but also to sustain the tools of the NanoCommons partners after the end of the project, the NanoCommons KI must support these tools if necessary, also financially in the starting phase or when major updates are needed, to keep them at the state-of-the-art. After recognising the potential of a certain tool or service, NanoCommons should offer the creator support for the integration of its tool/service into the NanoCommons KI. By offering its tool through the infrastructure, the creator would optimally be able to generate additional revenues, which would help them to further develop the tool/service but also the infrastructure, e.g., by service fees for using it. If the revenue is not enough for sustaining the tool, or if the creator, for whatever the reason, does not want to or cannot further develop it, a complete or partial take-over

of the development including transfer/purchase of IPRs by the NanoCommons consortium or a partner needs to be considered. This is especially the case for central parts of the NanoCommons KI. The NanoCommons Knowledge Base is one example for this, since it is absolutely essential for the infrastructure and the complete data management and sharing concept. While at a first glance this might suggest that revenue options are limited because of the EU open data directive which is fully endorsed by NanoCommons, and the ongoing efforts and collaborations of the NanoSafety community to share data worldwide (e.g., EU-US and EU-ANF collaborations). However, data management is time-consuming and requires training, support and “shepherding” to comply with the requirements of the open data pilot, and thus this offers an opportunity whereby future projects could purchase open-data management services and expertise tailored to their specific needs from NanoCommons, with costs to support their data management needs across the entire project lifecycle and to integrate their data into the NanoCommons Knowledge Base written into those new projects. For example, NanoCommons has introduced the concept of a “data shepherd” as someone who has knowledge of both the experimental and data management needs and can guide (herd) project participants in the correct processes for data management. These concepts of the nanosafety data life cycle and the data shepherd have been described in Deliverable D3.1 – Initial guidance on emerging data and metadata standards, and in a publication by Papadiamantis *et al.*, 2020.

WP10 deliverables D10.5 and D10.6, during the final period of the project, will report on the further development of the GUIDEnano tool, as well as the decisions and lessons learnt from the past, in order to include all these experiences into the guidance process of the NanoCommons KI.

2) Elements of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan

Progress on the elements of the NanoCommons sustainability plan (D10.3) is analysed.

As defined in the initial version of the NanoCommons sustainability plan (D10.3¹⁷) the main steps in developing the sustainability plan are:

1. Definition of the NanoCommons KI's aim;
2. Definition of the NanoCommons KI's content and structure;
3. Definition of access to and business models for the NanoCommons KI;
4. Definition of the contributors and users of the NanoCommons KI;
5. Definition of the services and tools provided by the NanoCommons KI;
6. Definition of trainings: teaching the contributors and users to use the infrastructure and its content in a proper way;
7. Support service for users and contributors of the infrastructure.

Progress towards these steps is described in more detail in the subsections below.

NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI)

Aim of the NanoCommons KI

Since the beginning of the project, significant efforts have been directed towards achieving the main objective of NanoCommons which is to: “create a *nanosafety knowledge infrastructure* that organises and visualises data and data relationships, makes it accessible, integrates computational tools for risk assessment and decision support, enables their validation and facilitates the necessary grouping of these tools and services into a coherent offer for the nanosafety community and stakeholders”.

Content and structure of the NanoCommons KI

The NanoCommons KI is developing the tools and workflows needed to provide a standardised, reproducible and interoperable way to access all available nanosafety data, knowledge, analysis and modelling tools/services that have been adapted and verified as suitable for application to safety assessment of NMs, complying with the needs and expectations of the European nanosafety, nanomedicine and emerging materials research and regulatory communities. The NanoCommons KI consists of two heavily interlinked subsystems, the *NanoCommons services* and the *NanoCommons consulting activities*. The first consists of data and nanoinformatics tools which build the basis of many TA offerings but can also be accessed via the NanoCommons services website¹⁸ for self-learners. These services and their improved findability and accessibility are the physical realisation of the KI as an integrated data and methods management infrastructure, enhancing the interoperability and

¹⁷ https://zenodo.org/record/3603179#.Xt_wlsBCTRY

¹⁸ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/e-infrastructure/transnational-access-services/>

reusability of nano-related data and associated protocols, together with the data modelling tools and services and the resulting models. The [NanoCommons KI](#)¹⁹ was launched at the end of 2019. More details about its content can be found in this deliverable under the sections “Services and Tools provided by the NanoCommons KI” and “Online Training”. The second component is the expertise demonstrated via the work performed by the NanoCommons experts in collaboration with NanoCommons users of the TA projects, which will be continued beyond the project as the provision of consultancy services.

The **NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure** (KI) is underpinned by a number of technical components, two of which are introduced here since they are often mentioned within the deliverable and might lead to confusion, due to their similarity. These are, the **NanoCommons Knowledge Base** (KB) and the **NanoCommons Data Warehouse** (DW). The *NanoCommons KB* is the central component of the NanoCommons data management system and is what provides the functionality that converts data to knowledge. It consists of the specific semantic mapping of concepts and ontologies commonly applied in Nanoinformatics and Nanotoxicology research used to integrate, as many as possible, important data sources into the NanoCommons KI. In this way, it offers global visualisation, search and browsing features to all the data in the sources both, via a web-based graphical user interface and API, combined with tools to enrich data using complex queries and to create reports based on all extracted evidence. In contrast, the service for storing data (i.e., achieving it and facilitating its accessibility) as the *NanoCommons DW*. This is just one of the data sources indexed in the NanoCommons KB, which includes also the eNanoMapper and soon the ACEnano DWs, and is used currently to store, manage and share data from the NanoMILE and NanoFASE projects and is proposed as the data storage solution in many TAs, like the one within the SmartNanoTox project. Both, the NanoCommons KB and the DW, went online in March 2020 and are accessible under the NanoCommons [website](#)²⁰. The user only sees one interface for both and the differentiation is only important for presenting the NanoCommons data concepts of interlinked DWs underpinning the NanoCommons KB and for the preparation of new TA applications in order to understand if the applicants are looking for physical storage of their data or if they want to integrate an existing or under-development DW already holding their (project) data.

NanoCommons is an infrastructure, not just a catalogue of services. The services and tools that are offered through the NanoCommons KI are interrelated. A key aspect of all the user case studies, including the industrial ones, introduced in deliverable D10.3 with an update report provided later in this document, is to demonstrate the added-value from the integration aspects provided by NanoCommons, i.e., the harmonisation of nanosafety data and its structuring and provision for direct use in nanoinformatics tools and services structured in sophisticated workflows to support NMs risk assessment and safe by design approaches.

The integrated tools and services aim to address the following issues:

- extracting knowledge from raw experimental data (e.g., microscopic images or spectral data),
- pre-processing the data before they are sent to modelling services (normalisation, missing data handling, selection of important variables, dimensionality reduction),

¹⁹ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/>

²⁰ <https://ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons>

- generating theoretical descriptors (such as structural or quantum mechanical descriptors),
- analysing big -omics or “corona-related” data in terms of identifying the biological mechanisms and pathways associated with toxicity and other adverse effects and producing aggregated biologically enriched descriptors,
- harmonising and integrating diversity of data and metadata originating from heterogeneous resources, so that homogeneous datasets suitable for modelling are produced,
- semantically retrieving ontology annotated data from the public sources including but not limited to the NanoCommons DW and,
- continuous support of the NanoCommons Users to ensure optimal training and use of the integrated tools.

As a result, the services so far implemented in the NanoCommons KI include:

- Datasets and Knowledge Base included within the NanoCommons KB:
 - NanoMILE physicochemical characterisation library and *in vitro* toxicity data
 - NanoFASE NMs physicochemical characterisation and environmental fate and transformations library
 - eNanoMapper database and related project data warehouses
 - Further integrations are already planned:
 - ACEnano data warehouse
 - The Nanomaterial-Biological Interactions (NBI) Knowledgebase
 - OECD NanoAOP database
 - EdelweissData management system (as part of the ACEnano data warehouse but also independently)
- Data management tools and workflows:
 - Electronic notebooks
 - Data and metadata curation
 - Semantic annotation of data and metadata
 - Protocols and methods repository
- Development and implementation of experimental workflows:
 - ENM physicochemical characterisation
 - Ecotoxicology
 - Protein corona characterisation (proteins, lipids, metabolites)
 - High-throughput screening approaches
- Tailored nanosafety assessment strategies:
 - Development and implementation of *safe by design* strategies
- Risk assessment and mitigation strategies:
 - GUIDEnano tool
 - Integrated web-based decision support system for regulators combining the GUIDEnano and Jaqpot tools with the AOP-based prediction of points of departure via the Enalos Cloud Platform
- Omics data analysis:
 - Evaluation of data quality
 - Normalisation

- Differential expression analysis
- Functional enrichment analysis
- Network reconstruction
- *In silico* modelling:
 - Statistical modelling, data-driven NM property and functionality prediction via QSARs
 - Materials modelling, physics-based NM property prediction
 - PBPK models
 - Prediction of NMs bionano interactions
 - Prediction of Molecular Initiating Events (MIEs) as first step to Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)
 - Machine learning models
- Image analysis tools:
 - NanoImage - NM descriptors from TEM images
 - NanoXtract - NM descriptors from TEM images
 - DeepDaph analysis of NM toxicity to *Daphnia magna* from light microscopy images of the daphnids using machine learning
- Dedicated Helpdesk

More details about the services implemented so far, can be found in the sub-section “Services and Tools provided by the NanoCommons KI”.

Access to and business models for the NanoCommons KI

NanoCommons promotes *fairness*, open data and open source software. However, maintenance of the KI and the services including (i) guaranteeing the availability of data and services in the future and (ii) continuous developments and improvements to follow the scientific progress and to fulfil the scientific and regulatory requirements, requires ongoing funding. To address this, NanoCommons business model and plan are presented and analysed, in detail, under the section *Business Concept for NanoCommons*. However, it already became clear that different services will have specific requirements, as this may generate a conflict of interests, e.g., the global goal expressed by the EU Commission towards open data and open science, compared to commercial and competitive advantages. Therefore, the access to NanoCommons resources will be defined on a case-by-case basis, starting in the next deliverable D10.5.

Contributors to and Users of the NanoCommons KI

NanoCommons expects to have external **contributors**, who will enrich the KI with new tools / models / data, but preferably also directly supporting the core infrastructure. At this point of the project it is still unclear if those services will run directly in the KI or if they will stay hosted by the service providers (as is the case now). This topic will be assessed in the next deliverables (D10.5 and D10.6).

Users of the NanoCommons KI include:

- SMEs – producing or incorporating NMs into their products and solutions;
- Large companies – producing or incorporating NMs in their products and solutions;
- Regulators – evaluating regulatory issues associated with NMs in products;
- Policy makers – evaluating policy issues associated with NMs in products;
- Researchers and Scientists – supporting the use of data and tools in their research activities.

Besides the contributors and users of the NanoCommons KI, there are also **Strategic Collaborators**: they act as multipliers which could lead to more customers by endorsing NanoCommons. To the strategic collaborators already identified in D10.3 (i.e., ELIXIR, OECD, EUON, European Risk Governance Council and EPPN), three new strategic collaborators are being addressed (NanoSafety Cluster, EOSC and ETPN). The status of the recent activities and interactions with these strategic collaborators is monitored in Table 1.

Table 1. Activities with the Strategic Collaborators.

Strategic Collaborator	Activity / Interaction
<p>EU NanoSafety Cluster (NSC)</p>	<p>The NSC²¹ is the most important <i>strategic collaborator</i> since NanoCommons is designed to be the infrastructure for its nanosafety community. NanoCommons is very well represented in the NSC coordination team & secretariat as well as in all NSC Working Groups (WG) (Martin Himly (PLUS, chair of WG A), Costas Chariditis (NTUA, chair of WG B), Claus Svendsen and Soco Vázquez (UKCEH and LEITAT, chairs of subgroup WG C-3), Antreas Afantitis (NovaM, Co-chair WG D and member of the core group in WG G) and Egon Willighagen and Thomas Exner (MU and EwC, chair and co-chair of WG F)). This places NanoCommons in a very strategic position to promote NanoCommons' data management services to other NSC projects.</p> <p>Furthermore, the NanoCommons online trainings/webinars have jointly been organized with the NSC WG A Communication, Training and Education. The attendance at these educational events helps us assess the community needs and therefore guides us in our main aim of achieving sustainability beyond the project end. The participants of the training sessions become, upon completion, a certificate of attendance; the certificates are jointly awarded by NanoCommons and the NSC.</p> <p>NanoCommons also supports the community, with continued ontology development, initiating in April 2019 a new service: the European Registry of Materials. Following similar practices in the drug discovery</p>

²¹ <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/>

	<p>field, projects can register materials with a unique, global and persistent identifier, without disclosing much information outside the project. This identifier can then be used to <i>FAIR</i>-ly identify the material while having full control over information communication and dissemination. At the time of writing, over eighty materials were registered. These data came from the projects NanoSolveIT, NanoFASE, RiskGONE, NanoTest and caLIBRAte.</p>
<p>European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)</p>	<p>NanoCommons had a very good interaction and feedback with representatives of the EOSC²² at the final OpenRiskNet workshop (22-24 October 2019, Amsterdam). During this meeting, NanoCommons decided to become more closely attached to the developments going on by applying to the Early Adopter Programme of EOSC-hub. Since open data and open science is one of the major goals of the new EU calls (final H2020 calls, but even more importantly in Horizon Europe), NanoCommons is taking this opportunity, improving its chances for successful applications in the future, getting on the EOSC marketplace and getting contact to other big players in the EOSC arena. Exchange of information related to possible ways to sustain open data and open science infrastructure, beyond public funding by the EU, was especially important for the development of the business plans presented here.</p>
<p>ELIXIR</p>	<p>ELIXIR²³ aims to “unite Europe’s leading life science organisations in managing and safeguarding the increasing volume of data being generated by publicly funded research”. Toxicology resources are important to them and have links to various of their other activities. A Toxicology Community is being set up (“emerging”) and various NanoCommons partners are involved in this effort. Collaboration with the ELIXIR Training and Compute Platforms are some of the crosslinks between NanoCommons and ELIXIR, which will benefit both organisations by merging the offerings for material design and safety and will, in this way, help to extend the user base.</p> <p>NanoCommons has already begun by sharing and promoting its training materials <i>via</i> the TeSS²⁴, ELIXIR’s Training Portal. This will also be done for the events in order to prompt them to a wider community.</p>

²² <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/>

²³ <https://elixir-europe.org/>

²⁴ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/about>

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	<p>The Malta Initiative is an European Action to develop OECD²⁵ Test Guidelines for NMs and, therefore, has as one of its aims to develop and amend the test guidelines (TG) and guidance documents (GD) to ensure that nano-specific issues for fulfilling regulatory requirements are addressed.</p> <p>NanoCommons is actively approaching specific regulatory issues via two Industrial Case Studies: (i) Case Study 3 (on the extension of skin sensitization assessment methods to nanoforms) and (ii) Case Study 5 (defining vocabulary for OECD guidelines that can be used in NanoCommons applications supporting assessment and testing nanoforms). Being at the forefront of such activities is bringing more attention to the NanoCommons project (and, with this, the NanoCommons KI) and promoting the use of NanoCommons services and workflows for both, data management and integrated risk assessment.</p>
European Union Observatory for Nanomaterials (EUON)	<p>The EUON²⁶, hosted and maintained by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), provides information about existing nanomaterials on the EU market. To support this information by underlying evidence down to the primary data, the eNanoMapper database was linked into the observatory. This allows searches in the datasets generated by different projects and other primary data providers. NANoREG tops the list, being the largest provider with almost 40,000 data points. Since the NanoCommons KI and specifically the NanoCommons KB would offer access to more data sources (including eNanoMapper,) and advanced features to perform searches across all of these, a collaboration between EUON and NanoCommons has been initiated to develop the technical solutions to integrate the NanoCommons KI in the EUON offerings. The main discussion points currently are, if the NanoCommons user interface is just linked into EUON, or if the meta-search capacities are more deeply integrated into the EUON platform.</p>
European Risk Governance Council – Risk Governance of Nanomaterials: 3 European Projects	<p>To boost the effect and synergies between the funded projects addressing governance and nanoinformatics, an interaction commitment between the projects Gov4Nano²⁷, NANORIGO²⁸ and RiskGONE²⁹ has been agreed. These three projects will develop a framework and a portal for the envisaged European Nano Risk</p>

²⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/>

²⁶ <https://euon.echa.europa.eu/>

²⁷ <https://www.gov4nano.eu/>

²⁸ <http://nanorigo.eu/>

²⁹ <https://riskgone.eu/>

<p>Working Together: Gov4Nano & NANORIGO & RiskGONE</p>	<p>Governance Council, where tools and data management will play a key role. An inter-project core group on data management has been formed that will link the NanoCommons KI with the NRGC portal and framework. NanoCommons is feeding directly into this grouping and supporting the development of the decision support tools for the NRGC, and the integration of datasets and tools to facilitate risk assessment.</p>
<p>European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs (EPPN)</p>	<p>NanoCommons has been interacting with the EPPN³⁰ in order to share its know-how and help the pilot projects in bringing their research to the next level, addressing interesting topics for individual projects or collectively via the EPPN.</p> <p>The first approach took place on November 5th, 2019 in San Sebastian (Spain). NanoCommons was invited to participate in an EPPN workshop. The project was presented as an initiative supporting the pilots by providing access NanoCommons expertise (in nanoinformatics and data management tools, modelling and risk assessment services) free of charge (by means of TA³¹ activities). The goal was to raise awareness among EPPN partners and facilitate them to take advantage of the NanoCommons services, facilities and knowledge to advance their work, solve problems and take their research to the next level. 5% of the participants filled in the NanoCommons online survey, showing their interest for the project and their outcome. More details can be found in Deliverable D2.5 (2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations).</p> <p>The EPPN (and/or its potential successor SusNanoFab project³²) as a potential individual Case Study for development within the scope of the WP9 is still being considered and will be approached in year 4 of the project (2021).</p>
<p>Nanomedicine European Technology Platform (ETPN)</p>	<p>As a part of the extended nanosafety community, the ETPN³³, especially the working group safety & characterisation, shall become a core collaborator with all the EU funded projects gaining nanosafety-relevant data e.g., EU-NCL (finished), NOBEL (CSA, connection point for further interaction), REFINE (regulatory framework nanomedicine - should benefit from NanoCommons KI), BIORIMA (mixture between nanosafety and nanomedicine), etc.</p>

³⁰ <https://www.eppnetwork.com/>

³¹ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/ta-access/>

³² <https://susnanofab.eu/>

³³ <https://etp-nanomedicine.eu>

	<p>Dissemination and promotion actions of the NanoCommons project via the ETPN have been started, enhancing the chance of collaborations and interactions with more projects and, at the same time, making a step forward to interlink both nanosafety and medicine communities. One important next step would be to promote the online training sessions organised by NanoCommons within the ETPN bench community including our nanoinformatics and data management tools, modelling and risk assessment services.</p>
--	---

During the project lifetime, all customers and users of the NanoCommons KI are accessing the services and tools via the TAs and/or the case studies (research, demonstration or industrial). The analysis and evaluation of all these activities will support the overall evaluation of the NanoCommons business plan and provide evidence to demonstrate the added value provided by NanoCommons.

Services and Tools

One of the main objectives of the NanoCommons KI is to offer the community (i) nanoinformatics, (ii) data management tools and (iii) modelling and risk assessment services.

Since the very beginning of the project (M3), NanoCommons has been assessing the needs of the community via an *online survey*³⁴, in order to meet them and to offer NanoCommons “potential” customers the tools and services they need/are interested in. The actual results of the survey³⁵ are shown in *Annex 1*. The results of the survey are regularly monitored in order to answer the requests of the potential users and the community, offering them the services and tools they need via the NanoCommons KI.

All services and tools³⁶ being offered by the project are currently available as TAs via the corresponding subsite on the project webpage. A detailed list of the current (December 2020) tools and services is available in *Annex 2*.

Online Training

NanoCommons offers the opportunity to users and contributors of getting trained in many of the services and tools provided by the NanoCommons KI. Currently available training material is summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Available Online Training Tools.

³⁴ NanoCommons Online Survey to identify the needs of the community:

³⁵ <https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/PK2KXWW>

³⁶ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/services>

TA service category	Nanoinformatics services	Training formats	Level of training material
Experimental Workflows	Physico-Chemical characterization protocols NMs corona / eco-corona characterisation protocols NMs ecotoxicity protocols (e.g., Daphnia)	Written tutorial	Basic
Data Processing & Analysis	Biomax data templates	Recorded webinar	Basic
	NIKC data templates	Written tutorial	Advanced
	Jaqpot platform	Demo video	Advanced
		Demo video	Expert
	Enalos NanoXtract for TEM analysis	Demo video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
	Biocorona <i>in silico</i> modelling	Recorded webinar	Advanced
	OpenRiskNet e-infrastructure	Recorded webinars incl. demo videos	Basic
		Recorded webinars incl. videos and documentations	Advanced
	Data Visualization and Toxicity Prediction	Enalos cloud for Zeta potential	Demo video
Enalos cloud for Safe-by-Design		Recorded webinar	Basic
Enalos cloud for Safe-by-Design		Demo video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
GUIDEnano		Recorded webinar	Basic
Data Storage	SciNote	Demo video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
	ACEnano Knowledge Infrastructure	Online tutorial	Basic

Within the NanoCommons KI³⁷, under the Library section³⁸ (see Figure 5), NanoCommons has made available all the resources offered to date: tutorials, videos, webinars, documentation. By regularly organising online training events, the list of resources is steadily growing. Recorded webinars are uploaded to the *NanoCommons YouTube channel*³⁹ and indexed in the NanoCommons KI. These training materials are also automatically uploaded to the “NanoCommons channel⁴⁰” in TeSS⁴¹, ELIXIR’s training platform. The upcoming events will also be promoted via the TeSS Training Portal.

Figure 5. Overview of the NanoCommons *Knowledge Infrastructure*.

A detailed description of the NanoCommons catalogue of services and the associated training activities and related materials are detailed in deliverable D8.2 (First Report on Training Activities, focussing on virtual tools).

The list of training activities that have been organised by NanoCommons to date can be found in the NanoCommons KI, under Events⁴².

³⁷ www.infrastructure.nanocommons.eu

³⁸ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/library/>

³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuawpRvXNpplwyltefTctw>

⁴⁰ https://tess.elixir-europe.org/content_providers/nanocommons

⁴¹ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁴² <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/events/>

Support Service – Helpdesk

NanoCommons has established a helpdesk and associated support services for contributors and users of the NanoCommons KI. The Helpdesk acts as a central point to support users in developing their applications.

The Helpdesk can be used for general inquiries, for submission of TAs or issues related with TAs, for suggestions and/or any technical issues.

A section with the FAQs has also been prepared and can be found on the project [website](#)⁴³.

Visitors can contact the Helpdesk filling in a [form](#)⁴⁴ on the project website, or by sending the support team an email with their inquiry.

More details about the NanoCommons Helpdesk are described in Deliverable 7.1 (Initial Helpdesk Service platform, including User Guidance and Tutorials)⁴⁵.

Status of activities to implement the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan

The current status of activities performed to contribute to the sustainability of the NanoCommons KI are analysed, taking the key performance indicators as measures of their successful development. Activities for the remaining period that will ensure the sustainability of the NanoCommons KI are defined.

NanoCommons has identified activities that generate awareness of, and drive user traffic to the NanoCommons project tools and KB as contributing to its sustainability, and seeks commitments from partners and actions to embed the infrastructure into permanent or long-term structures such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) or EUON as providing sustainability.

The project timeline below (see Figure 6) shows where we have come from, where we are and where we are heading to:

⁴³ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/e-infrastructure/frequently-asked-questions/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/contact/>

⁴⁵ Confidential deliverable. Available upon request.

Figure 6. Project timeline – Status M35. Note due to Covid-19 the project will seek a 6-month extension and thus the total duration will be 54 months.

An overview of the already started activities that *contribute* to the sustainability of the NanoCommons KI are listed in Table 3. It summarises the activities of all project partners until the finalisation of this deliverable. Each element contributing to sustainability is aligned to the corresponding “Element of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan” (see corresponding section). The monitoring of the status is done with a traffic light system (green-achieved, yellow-ongoing, red-not achieved). These elements will be monitored in the next deliverables D10.5 (Second Testing and Evaluation Results of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan) and D10.6 (Final Version of NanoCommons Sustainability Plan) in M36 and M48, respectively.

For more details about the status of each of these activities, see the referenced deliverables⁴⁶.

Table 3. Overview of the activities contributing to the sustainability of NanoCommons.

Element	Reference	KPI	Status M35
NanoCommons website	www.nanocommons.eu	Website online No. of visits Link to website from other platforms	Website online & content being updated regularly
Integration of data (KB) into the NanoCommons KI	ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons/ D3.1 ⁴⁷ D3.4 ⁴⁸	Metadata guidelines defined Online and accessible	Internal-testing version available in 2019 Live version available

⁴⁶ All public NanoCommons deliverables are available at the project webpage (<https://www.nanocommons.eu/news-events/outputs/>), and in the NanoCommons Community on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/nanocommons/search?page=1&size=20&subtype=deliverable>).

⁴⁷ Confidential deliverable pending approval by EU. Available upon request.

⁴⁸ Confidential deliverable pending approval by EU. Available upon request.

	D4.1 ⁴⁹ D4.2 ⁵⁰ D4.4 D4.5 ⁵¹		since March 2020
Integration of nanoinformatics tools into the NanoCommons KI	Infrastructure.nanocommons.eu D5.2 D5.3 D5.4 D5.5 D5.6 D5.7	Website online Nr. of visits	Website online KnowledgeBase online and accepting data input
Dissemination Pack	Project brochure, TA Flyer, general poster/rollup banner, standard presentation, project presentations and YouTube videos	At website In printed form	Supporting efforts to raise awareness of, drive user traffic to NanoCommons
Public deliverables	All project public deliverables	Public deliverables have been given a DOI through Zenodo and published online in the "Outputs and deliverables" and "Library" sections	Currently 15 deliverable reports publicly available
Data Management Plan	D10.1 D10.1 - v2.0	DMP online and available in Zenodo. Initial version was updated once (v2.0), and a second update with dataset-specific details is in preparation	Public report Re-used in other EU H2020 proposals (e.g., NanoSolveIT, RiskGone)
Identification of community needs	Online survey D10.2	Nr. of responses to the online survey	Ongoing process via feedback from training events etc.
Analysis of community needs	D10.2	Offered services aligned to community needs	Services online available - being updated and supplemented with training materials continuously
Scanning of potential new tools/services to be	Results of the online survey	Threshold: 40%, for the development of a new	Ongoing

⁴⁹ Confidential deliverable pending approval by EU. Available upon request.

⁵⁰ Confidential deliverable. Available upon request.

⁵¹ Confidential deliverable. Available upon request.

developed		service	
Identification of users, customers, strategic collaborators	D10.2 D10.3 D10.4	Via dissemination and communication activities	Development of tailored communication & dissemination actions for each group underway
Interaction with users and customers	D7.2 D9.2 All TA WPs	Nr. of successful activities (TAs, attendance to training, attendance to events...)	More details about the events attended and TA activities in the corresponding deliverables
Interaction with strategic collaborators	D9.2 D10.3 D10.4	Nr. of successful activities (TAs, attendance to training...)	
Identification of Projects that may benefit from NanoCommons Services	D10.2	D10.2	Done. Shortlisted a group to engage with initially
Interaction with identified Projects	D2.6 (2021) All TA WPs	D2.6 (2021) Direct communication with identified projects Actions with identified projects	Ongoing (projects identified, actions started)
Identification funding Programs that may benefit from NanoCommons	D10.2	D10.2	Done. Related programs have been identified.
Interaction with identified Programs	D2.6 (2021)	D2.6 (2021)	Ongoing (programs identified. Actions to be started)
Definition of Demonstration Case Studies	D9.2	D9.2	3 case studies have been defined. More to come.
Identification of Industrial Case Studies	D10.3 D10.4	D10.3 D10.4	Ongoing - 9 industrial case studies have been identified
Actions towards Industrial Case Studies	D10.3 D10.4	D10.3 D10.4	Ongoing - Actions started
Research Case Studies - TAs	D7.2 All TA WPs	1st and 2nd Calls, done. Several TA awarded and started/ongoing/finished	Ongoing

		Details at project website	
Development of Services & Tools	All JRA WPs (WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6)	Services Online available	Ongoing
Training Activities	D8.1 D8.2 D2.5	Training Tools online available	Several online training sessions have been organised & conducted
Engagement of Stakeholders	D9.1 (to be delivered in 2021)	Ongoing engagement with EUON and ESOC	Ongoing
Identification of potential users in new member states	D2.4	55 members states have been identified and contacted	Ongoing
Interaction & integration of users from new member states	D2.4	Interaction with 17 new member states Events being organised at new member states	Ongoing
NanoCommons Business models	D10.3 D10.4		First version in D10.4
NanoCommons Business plan	D10.4	D10.4	First version in D10.4. To be updated in D10.5 and D10.6

These activities will be further monitored and updates will be given in the next WP10 deliverables . Additionally, new activities will be started and analysed in the remaining time to ensure the sustainability of the NanoCommons KI beyond project end. This includes the following activities foreseen for after project end:

- UoB's commitment to sustain the NanoCommons KI.
- Assure the sustainability of the NanoCommons KB (developed by Biomax) by providing a non-exclusive development license of the NanoCommons KB to UoB for long term maintenance.
- NanoCommons beneficiaries' commitments to sustain their services.
- Recruit external partners to provide services to be included in the NanoCommons KI portfolio.
- Engage with Strategic Collaborators to maintain their offers to promote the NanoCommons KI (e.g., EOSC and EUON).
- Engage with the Regional Champions/new member states for promoting NanoCommons offerings within their communities assuring the channelling of information, activities and opportunities (within the scope of NanoCommons) for the new member states.

NanoCommons Case Studies

Within the initial version of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan (Deliverable 10.3), we developed

and initiated a process for identifying and developing contacts for industrial case studies (paying special attention to the new regulations of the GDPR when handling contact information).

The aim of NanoCommons to establish an infrastructure for *in silico* nanosafety is ambitious. NanoCommons is working on identifying (i) if there is a market and a need for such an entity and (ii) if it provides a sufficient return for the risk and investment, including considerations on whether and how it has best leverage as part of a broader offering.

Within NanoCommons, three different kinds of cases studies have been identified:

- *Research case studies* (from TA activities showing how NanoCommons tools and services can support the community in their research);
- *Demonstration case studies* (arising from JRA activities and selected by the consortium partners to showcase the added-value from integration as a research infrastructure rather than being a set of disparate tools) and
- *Industrial case studies* (from NA activities and focussed on specific stakeholder groups as a means to assess the sustainability of the NanoCommons services).

The **research case studies** are essentially the NanoCommons *Transnational Access (TA)* projects, wherein nanosafety researchers from industry, academia and regulatory bodies apply to access the state-of-the-art NanoCommons expertise, free of charge, and take advantage of the NanoCommons services, facilities and knowledge to advance their work, solve problems and take their research to the next level. They focus on standardisation of data generation workflows across the disparate communities and establishment of a common access procedure for transnational and/or virtual access to the data, and modelling and risk prediction/management tools developed and integrated. The TAs are available via 6-monthly TA calls and every user can apply for them as a “mini-project”. The already [awarded TA projects](#)⁵² (research case studies) are available on the project website.

The **demonstration case studies** are intended to integrate across a range of services offered by the NanoCommons KB, and *demonstrate* the new capabilities that arise from integration, linking and facilitating communication between existing tools and resources. Within the project, and specifically in WP9, different Demonstration Case Studies are defined by the consortium in order to showcase and highlight the capabilities and potential of the NanoCommons KI. The first demonstration case studies that have been evaluated focus on the following three themes (more details can be found within Deliverable D9.2 “First Demonstration Case Studies”):

1. *Case Study 1*: Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) for data collection and annotation.
2. *Case Study 2*: Alignment of *in silico* protein corona modelling with experimental analysis.
3. *Case Study 3*: Data management concept and workflow for ecotoxicological information on potential environmental release of MNM as derived from the NanoFASE projec.

NanoCommons is planning to add new case studies in the next few months. Ideas being considered and developed currently, and which will be narrowed down to a further 3 case studies to take forward actively include:

⁵² <https://www.nanocommons.eu/e-infrastructure/awarded-ta-projects/>

- Best-practice in SOP development
- Best-practice in study design → How to plan the lab needs?
- Combining data from multiple data warehouses
- Harmonisation across platforms (including NCS platforms but also ELIXIR → ELIXIR community-driven implementation study)
- Requirements for achieving regulatory acceptance of nanoinformatics workflows
- Support of pilot production facilities and innovation hubs.

The **Industrial Cases Studies** are *user case studies* from customers and are intended as a means to assess the value of the services to the stakeholders and what future customers might be willing to pay for. They were defined within WP10 under Task 10.2 (Sustainability Plan) and Task 10.3 (Iteratively Test and Evaluate the Sustainability Plan and Model), in order to identify potential users of the NanoCommons KI, and to showcase how NanoCommons can solve their needs. The goal with these case studies is that the clients / users will provide testimonials about the added value that NanoCommons brought and will act as ambassadors for NanoCommons. Thus, the WP10 Industrial Case Studies are intended to provide the users with examples on specific services that can later be rolled out with a cost model. NanoCommons will actively engage with these pre-identified potential users to identify problems they have that can be solved by NanoCommons. WP10 will feed the generated requirements back into the KI development work to optimize solutions to the users' needs. Starting in 2019, NanoCommons has been working on these industrial case studies, developing conversations with the market, determining problems to be solved, and trying to provide a matching and prioritisation where NanoCommons can provide solutions addressing real business needs. These activities will continue until the project ends.

These identified cases studies will help NanoCommons to screen the market and to be able to generate a business plan for NanoCommons, based on the gained experiences, evaluating the value of the offered services and the estimation of costs:

- How to identify potential users, how to contact them and how to gain their confidence;
- How to elicit and capture the needs of the user;
- Once a need is identified, which is the expected service by the user;
- Estimation of Costs: resources needed for the implementation of the service (time invested in the scoping of the case study and implementation of it, personnel costs, etc.);
- Added-value of NanoCommons services;
- How to make the services more valuable to the users;
- Are users interested in paying for the services and what for and how much?

One of the main objectives of these case studies is to prove, after initial consultancy and training, if the case study partners are able to access and use the NanoCommons services on their own, increasing the sustainability of the NanoCommons KI.

3) Business Concept for NanoCommons

The business concept for NanoCommons is presented, defining the NanoCommons Organisation and its content.

The main aim of Task 10.2 - *Sustainability Plan for NanoCommons* is to create a business concept for NanoCommons, to achieve **economic sustainability** for the KI after the project ends. Further work will **evaluate and refine** the business models during the project duration and create a final **business plan**; this is done within Task 10.3 - *Iteratively Test and Evaluate the Sustainability Plan and Model*.

During the 6th General Assembly of NanoCommons (M30 - 21-22 September 2020), BNN presented the elaborated Business Concept for NanoCommons to the consortium in order to discuss potential shortcomings, gain feedback from partners on the different potential business models and discuss the next steps for the creation of the business plan. The results of these discussions and the follow-up activities are included herein. All presented estimations of costs/revenues are preliminary/provisional estimations and will be evaluated during the remaining project duration.

NanoCommons Organisation

The *NanoCommons Organisation* is the legal entity proposed to be established as the financial entity behind the *NanoCommons KI*. The *NanoCommons KI* consists of two blocks covering the different activities, namely (A) the consultancy and (B) the services, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. NanoCommons Business Concept.

Definition of each of the blocks:

- A. **Consultancy:** The NanoCommons Organisation would offer consultancy to its users/customers. This block refers to the time that the NanoCommons' experts spend when guiding/supporting a user when accessing/using one of NanoCommons services. Currently, it is the TA-time that TA-providers invest during the project runtime. Point of entry and place to find more information is

the TA section of the project website. The consultancy is currently being done within the scope of the four service categories (see Figure 7 for more details). On the basis of the TA reporting after the Reporting Period 2 (December 2020), more detailed information will be available about an estimation of costs, as a guidance for cost and revenue streams for commercial consultancy.

- B. **Services:** With this block, the integration of new services into the NanoCommons Organisation would be guaranteed. These services are included in the four categories defined (see Figure 7 for more details). This block is currently represented by the NanoCommons Infrastructure webpage⁵³, at the time of writing this deliverable, and includes both, (i) data services like technical support to include external data in the NanoCommons DW or linking external data to the NanoCommons KB, as well as (ii) nanoinformatics services including data enrichment, modelling, customised simulations and advanced risk assessment workflows.

These two blocks, the Consultancy and the Services, generate costs and provide revenues and are dependent on both internals and externals, where externals are currently mainly the partners in the TA projects (users) but would become more and more third parties in the form of strategic partnerships and service providers:

- A. Consultancy: Dependent on internals (e.g., project partners offering services) and externals (e.g., external organizations offering services via NanoCommons).
- B. Services: Dependent on internals (expertise, tools, data) and externals (expertise, tools, data).

IPR strategy

An analysis of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) has been carried out, to analyse how it could affect the economic sustainability of the NanoCommons KI after the project ends. Figure 8 presents the evolution of the IPR of all projects and the project's main aim of achieving a sustainable and economically viable NanoCommons Organisation, as an operative unit.

The *background IPRs*, before project start, are defined in the NanoCommons Consortium Agreement.

The *foreground IPRs* include the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of all NanoCommons partners that have been generated during the project runtime. These KERs are based on services that are provided during the project runtime by: (i) NanoCommons via JRAs and TAs⁵⁴, (ii) confidential deliverables, (iii) services and data already included in the NanoCommons KI⁵⁵, and (iv) consultancy and services offered via industrial case studies, demonstration case studies, and more. The catalogue of the NanoCommons KERs, identified and defined by each project partner, is listed in *Annex 3*.

⁵³ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.nanocommons.eu/e-infrastructure/transnational-access-services/>

⁵⁵ https://ssl.biomax.de/nanocommons/cgi/login_bioxm_portal.cgi

Figure 8. NanoCommons Timeline. Note the extension of the project to month 54 is expected.

4) NanoCommons Organisation's Business Plan

The business plan for the NanoCommons Organisation is presented and analysed.

We envision the NanoCommons Organisation as a one-stop-shop for nanosafety and nanoinformatics consultancy and knowledge services, where the customers can get what they need. The NanoCommons Organisation would function as the honest broker offering the core infrastructure and the catalogue of services, including consultancy offerings, promotion activities, matchmaking and interactions with the strategic collaborators; in sum, representing the manifestation of the NanoCommons KI. Additionally, maintenance of essential services can completely or partly be transferred to the Organisation. All other consultancy and services behind the NanoCommons KI are offered and managed by the corresponding providers after the initial mediation by the NanoCommons Organisation. In this way, the **NanoCommons Organisation can exist as an independent and possibly even non-for-profit organisation, while the consultancy and service providers behind the organisation have the full potential for commercial exploitation** of their services and to decide on their own business model, which might vary from open data and open source to fully closed pay-for-use services.

The business plan for the NanoCommons Organisation presented here thus only covers the core infrastructure. As both main components, the KI and KB, are absolutely essential for the sustainability of NanoCommons, these are expected to build the minimal portfolio of the NanoCommons Organisation and cost estimates and potential revenues are presented. The further evaluation and development of the business plan during the final period of the project will be based on results from the TA activities as well as discussions with the individual consortium and external partners, and will

be reported in deliverables D10.5 and D10.6, respectively.

The business plan is based on an initial evaluation of the business potential applying the business model Canvas⁵⁶, as presented in an initial form in D10.3. Due to the fact that confidential knowhow is generated, only a short summary is described here. Key partners, key activities and key resources have been identified, and additionally the potential of leveraging best practice from other e-infrastructures and knowledge bases assessed. The value propositions, the customer segments and groups (e.g., supra-national organisations addressing nanosafety; industry users; academic users) have been structured and channels to address those groups have been defined (see also section “Elements of the NanoCommons Sustainability Plan”). The cost structure and revenue streams are shown below.

Financial structure

A central part of the NanoCommons Organisation’s Business Plan are the financial aspects of the plan. Besides all administrative, strategic and content-oriented elements of the plan, a comparison of estimated *costs versus revenues* (see Table 4) is essential to assess the economic potential and prepare an implementation plan accordingly.

Table 4. Cost versus Revenues Analysis.

Block	Costs	Revenues
NanoCommons Organisation and core infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maintenance of the infrastructure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Software/Hardware ○ Administration staff ○ IT staff for maintenance ○ Administration time ○ Access/users. ● Indirect costs (building maintenance cost, IT, ...). ● Maintenance of existing data. ● Maintenance of existing services → Covered by service provider. ● After 5 years → Upgrade of NanoCommons KB to enable add-ons to existing data and services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User fees for accessing the knowledge infrastructure → Covered by (A) and/or (B). ● Fees for “Nanoinformatics Association” → Covered by (A) and/or (B). ● Participation in projects, as subcontractor or beneficiary
(A) Consultancy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administration staff. ● Experts staff. ● Indirect costs (building maintenance cost, IT, ...). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Customers → Procurement of consultancy (e.g. 10% of total order).

⁵⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business_Model_Canvas

(B) Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administration staff. ● Indirect costs (building maintenance cost, IT, ...). ● Integration of new services. ● Marketing staff. ● Contracting with service providers. ● Add-on to existing services → Update existing services / software. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Customers → Procurement of services (e.g., 10% of total order).
---------------------	--	---

Clarifications for Table 3:

- **NanoCommons Organisation and core infrastructure**: The costs associated with the NanoCommons Organisation and core infrastructure will be covered by the *access fees*. The possibility of requiring access fees for the KI (Basic versus Premium subscription) has been taken into account. The *basic* option would provide access to open access services, whereas the *premium* one would provide access to all services offered by the NanoCommons KI.

Since some services are essential for the operation of the infrastructure, e.g., the data sharing via the NanoCommons KB, they might therefore be considered part of the core infrastructure at one point of time. The increased cost to also support the core services might exceed the revenues from the license fees. Since all other services and the consultancy provision profit from these, service fees for procurement of the other services and consultancy contracts could be added.

An alternative possibility generating revenues to the KI would be the creation of a “*Nanoinformatics Association*”: all NanoCommons partners would become members of the association.

Finally, another non-exclusive possibility of generating revenues would be that the NanoCommons Organisation would be funded by follow-up projects, when participating as subcontractor or beneficiary of it. However, this is not ideal as seen from the GUIDEnano case study as it leads to complications regarding IPR and rights of previous and future consortium members and suggests that a viable market opportunity may not exist.

- **Consultancy**: To maintain the consultancy offering, costs associated with the NanoCommons Organisation for promoting the consultancy services and matchmaking will arise, in addition to the time required from the NanoCommons/external experts. We expect that the latter will be covered by the consultancy provider through the revenues from the consultancy contracts between the provider and the customer. In other words, we expect that the NanoCommons Organisation will adopt the role of a trusted broker facilitating and establishing consultancy services but transferring the legal and financial dealings to the actual consultant at least for the time directly after project end. As already mentioned before, the calculation of the revenues associated with the Consultancy will become clearer once the TA reporting is carried out after the Reporting Period 2 (December 2020), as more information will be available for detailed cost/benefit analysis of such services to evaluate their commercial attractiveness. This analysis

needs to consider that a service charge of a fixed percentage (e.g., 10%) of the total amount of the order needs to be added for the services provided by the NanoCommons Organisation.

- **Services:** The costs of developing and integrating new services into the NanoCommons KI will be covered by the service providers of those services through license agreements directly between the provider and the customer, similar to the approach described above for the consultancy projects. Also here, a fixed percentage (e.g. 10%) of the total amount of the order will cover the cost of supporting the integrating into the KI performed by the NanoCommons Organisation.

Costs

The Cost structure for the NanoCommons Organisation includes two main internal cost items, for which the estimated costs for the first 5 years after the end of NanoCommons project are shown in Tables 5a and 5b, provided by the IP owners of the NanoCommons KI and KB, respectively. The total costs are then shown in Table 6.

However, the IP owners do not necessarily correspond to the driver of the NanoCommons Organisation, i.e., the entity taking care of it and achieving its economic sustainability. The driver can be a new legal entity under the name NanoCommons Organisation, a NanoCommons Association, an individual NanoCommons partner or a joint venture of multiple partners. Which option to adopt will be refined in the subsequent deliverables (D10.5 and D10.6) but this entity has to assure that the IP owners will be compensated.

Table 5a. Estimation of Costs for NanoCommons KI.

NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure (KI)	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Fix costs						
Maintenance of the KI	€ 5 000,00	€ 5 250,00	€ 5 512,50	€ 5 788,13	€ 6 077,53	€ 6 381,41
Integration new Data	€ 15 000,00	€ 15 750,00	€ 16 537,50	€ 17 364,38	€ 18 232,59	€ 19 144,22
Update of all systems after 5 years runtime	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ 10 939,56
Integration of new Services	€ 10 000,00	€ 10 500,00	€ 11 025,00	€ 11 576,25	€ 12 155,06	€ 12 762,82
Variable costs						
Per User (60€ per user)	€ 6 000,00	€ 6 300,00	€ 6 615,00	€ 6 945,75	€ 7 293,04	€ 7 657,69
Total Costs KI	€ 36 000,00	€ 37 800,00	€ 39 690,00	€ 41 674,50	€ 43 758,23	€ 56 885,69

Table 5b. Estimation of Costs for driving the NanoCommons KB.

NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB)	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Fix costs						
Maintenance of the KB	€ 5 000,00	€ 5 250,00	€ 5 512,50	€ 5 788,13	€ 6 077,53	€ 6 381,41
Integration new Data	€ 20 000,00	€ 21 000,00	€ 22 050,00	€ 23 152,50	€ 24 310,13	€ 25 525,63
Update of all systems after 5 years runtime	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ -	€ 21 271,36
Integration of new Services	€ 20 000,00	€ 21 000,00	€ 22 050,00	€ 23 152,50	€ 24 310,13	€ 25 525,63
Variable costs						
Per User (250€ per user)	€ 25 000,00	€ 26 250,00	€ 27 562,50	€ 28 940,63	€ 30 387,66	€ 31 907,04
Total Cost KB	€ 70 000,00	€ 73 500,00	€ 77 175,00	€ 81 033,75	€ 85 085,44	€ 110 611,07

The costs are based on some estimations that are explained to make visible the potential shortcomings of this estimation. However, this will be assessed and (if needed) adapted during the project runtime.

- Fixed costs:
 - 5% increase in the costs per year has been considered.
 - Maintenance of the KI: software, hardware, IT staff, administration staff and access/users are the fixed costs that have been taken into account.
 - Integration of data: These are service costs, if a new dataset brings new requirements (new connections, new data types / endpoints) and the system has to be adapted. The maintenance of existing data has no extra cost beyond the general KI maintenance.
 - Integration of new services: The costs considered here include: software, hardware, marketing staff, contracting with service providers, as well as the integration of new services into the KI, which requires effort on the KI's driver side in addition to the effort from the Service Provider. The cost for the maintenance of the existing services will be covered by the corresponding service provider.
- Variable costs:
 - In the number of users, for the first year, the calculation has been done based on 100 users. An increase of 5 users per year has been considered.
 - Costs per user stay stable over time, but maintenance costs go up as the hardware needs to be scaled; the current set-up is for 10 concurrent users (usually serves about 100 infrequent named users) with focus on data access NOT analysis. If we need to scale to 1000 concurrent users the maintenance cost grow to about euro 60,000/year; similarly, if we need to provide an analysis platform with heavy computational power for corona model calculation or omics analysis the costs will increase.

After five years, a general update of all systems is planned, that enables the Organisation to perform its business with state-of-the-art infrastructure and tools. Thus, in 2027, the costs are higher than in other years in which only the continuous maintenance costs occur. The summary of all costs is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of estimated total costs, based on 100 users initially, a 5% increase in users annually, and a complete upgrading of all hardware / software after 5 years to ensure alignment with the emerging state of the art.

	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Costs						
Total Costs KI	€ 36 000,00	€ 37 800,00	€ 39 690,00	€ 41 674,50	€ 43 758,23	€ 56 885,69
Total Cost KB	€ 70 000,00	€ 73 500,00	€ 77 175,00	€ 81 033,75	€ 85 085,44	€ 110 611,07
Total Costs (excl. Credit)	€ 106 000,00	€ 111 300,00	€ 116 865,00	€ 122 708,25	€ 128 843,66	€ 167 496,76
<i>Cumulative costs</i>	€ 106 000,00	€ 217 300,00	€ 334 165,00	€ 456 873,25	€ 585 716,91	€ 753 213,67

Revenues

The core revenues are anticipated to come from subscription fees, participation in projects and procurement of consultancy and/or services, as shown in Table 7 and summarized in Table 7a. Besides

the presented revenues, further possibilities would be to get public EU funding as an overall e-infrastructure, becoming part of a bigger e-infrastructure (e.g., EOSC, Elixir) or integration into other EU-funded infrastructure projects.

The revenues for the Consultancy and Services are based on the costs for services that have been evaluated within the TAs and are listed in the list of NanoCommons KERs (i.e., Catalogue of services provided by NanoCommons), see *Annex 3* for a detailed list of the KERs.

Table 7. NanoCommons Organisation's revenue streams.

Block	Revenue Description	Variables	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027		
NanoCommons Organisation & core infrastructure	User fees for accessing the KI → Basic subscription	# Users personal	30	45	65	95	115	135		
		Fee per User	€100,00	€100,00	€100,00	€100,00	€100,00	€105,00		
		User Fees Basic	€3 000,00	€4 500,00	€6 500,00	€9 500,00	€11 500,00	€14 175,00		
	User fees for accessing the KI → Premium subscription	# users personal	5	15	35	55	65	75		
		Fee per User	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€525,00		
		User Fees Premium	€2 500,00	€7 500,00	€17 500,00	€27 500,00	€32 500,00	€39 375,00		
	Fees for "Nanoinformatics Association"	# Membership Org.	10	12	14	16	18	20		
		Fee	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€500,00	€525,00		
	Participation in projects (subcontractor/beneficiary)	Membership fees Org.	€5 000,00	€6 000,00	€7 000,00	€8 000,00	€9 000,00	€10 500,00		
		# projects	1	1	2	2	3	3		
		Budget per project project(s)	€35 000,00	€35 000,00	€35 000,00	€35 000,00	€35 000,00	€35 000,00		
	(A) Consultancy	Customers → Procurement of consultancy (e.g.10% of total order)	# Consultancy X	2	5	10	17	27	33	
Costs per consult. X			€4 500,00	€4 725,00	€4 961,25	€5 209,31	€5 469,78	€5 743,27		
% procurement			10	10	10	10	10	10		
revenue consult. X			€900,00	€2 362,50	€4 961,25	€8 855,83	€14 768,40	€18 952,78		
# Consultancy Y			1	3	7	9	9	10		
Costs per consult. Y			€10 000,00	€10 500,00	€11 025,00	€11 576,25	€12 155,06	€12 762,82		
% procurement			10	10	10	10	10	10		
revenue consult. Y			€1 000,00	€3 150,00	€7 717,50	€10 418,63	€10 939,56	€12 762,82		
(B) Services			Customers → Procurement of services (e.g.10% of total order)	# Service X	2	6	14	21	25	30
				Costs per service X	€3 000,00	€3 150,00	€3 307,50	€3 472,88	€3 646,52	€3 828,84
	% procurement	10		10	10	10	10	10		
	revenue Service X	€600,00		€1 890,00	€4 630,50	€7 293,04	€9 116,30	€11 486,53		
	# Service Y	1		3	7	9	10	12		
	Costs per service Y	€8 000,00		€8 400,00	€8 820,00	€9 261,00	€9 724,05	€10 210,25		
	% procurement	10		10	10	10	10	10		
	revenue Service Y	€800,00		€2 520,00	€6 174,00	€8 334,90	€9 724,05	€12 252,30		

Table 7a. Summary of revenue streams.

	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Revenues						
Total revenues KI/KB	€ 45 500,00	€ 53 000,00	€ 101 000,00	€ 115 000,00	€ 158 000,00	€ 169 050,00
Total revenues Consult.	€ 1 900,00	€ 5 512,50	€ 12 678,75	€ 19 274,46	€ 25 707,96	€ 31 715,60
Total revenues Services	€ 1 400,00	€ 4 410,00	€ 10 804,50	€ 15 627,94	€ 18 840,35	€ 23 738,84
Total Revenues	€ 48 800,00	€ 62 922,50	€ 124 483,25	€ 149 902,39	€ 202 548,30	€ 224 504,43
<i>Cumulative revenues</i>	€ 48 800,00	€ 111 722,50	€ 236 205,75	€ 386 108,14	€ 588 656,45	€ 813 160,88

Balance sheet

The balance sheet (see Table 8) of the NanoCommons Organisation includes the estimated revenues from the KI/KB (see Table 7), the Costs of KI/KB, bank costs (interest rate 3.5%) and the annual plus/minus calculation.

Table 8. NanoCommons Organisation's balance sheet.

	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027
Costs						
Total Costs KI	€ 36 000,00	€ 37 800,00	€ 39 690,00	€ 41 674,50	€ 43 758,23	€ 56 885,69
Total Cost KB	€ 70 000,00	€ 73 500,00	€ 77 175,00	€ 81 033,75	€ 85 085,44	€ 110 611,07
Total Costs (excl. Credit)	€ 106 000,00	€ 111 300,00	€ 116 865,00	€ 122 708,25	€ 128 843,66	€ 167 496,76
<i>Cumulative costs</i>	€ 106 000,00	€ 217 300,00	€ 334 165,00	€ 456 873,25	€ 585 716,91	€ 753 213,67
Revenues						
Total revenues KI/KB	€ 45 500,00	€ 53 000,00	€ 101 000,00	€ 115 000,00	€ 158 000,00	€ 169 050,00
Total revenues Consult.	€ 1 900,00	€ 5 512,50	€ 12 678,75	€ 19 274,46	€ 25 707,96	€ 31 715,60
Total revenues Services	€ 1 400,00	€ 4 410,00	€ 10 804,50	€ 15 627,94	€ 18 840,35	€ 23 738,84
Total Revenues	€ 48 800,00	€ 62 922,50	€ 124 483,25	€ 149 902,39	€ 202 548,30	€ 224 504,43
<i>Cumulative revenues</i>	€ 48 800,00	€ 111 722,50	€ 236 205,75	€ 386 108,14	€ 588 656,45	€ 813 160,88
Balance						
<i>Credit-costs</i>	€ -	-€ 2 002,00	-€ 3 765,28	-€ 3 560,36	-€ 2 601,39	€ -
<i>Annual plus/minus</i>	-€ 57 200,00	-€ 50 379,50	€ 3 852,97	€ 23 633,79	€ 71 103,25	€ 57 007,67
Balance	-€ 57 200,00	-€ 107 579,50	-€ 101 724,53	-€ 74 325,46	€ 338,14	€ 59 947,21

According to this outline business plan, it would be possible to reach a break-even of annual revenues versus costs in year 3. The business will have a positive cumulative balance from the fifth year (see Figures 9a and 9b) onwards.

Figure 9a & 9b. Break-even of annual and cumulative costs.

5) Next steps during the final period of the project

Future plans and initiatives within NanoCommons to achieve further acceptance and usage of the NanoCommons KI by the wider community are presented, to support its long-term sustainability.

Further testing and evaluation of the NanoCommons Organisation's Business Plan will be reported in deliverables D10.5 and D10.6, based on the analysis and monitoring of the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the developments within the NanoCommons project.

Within the project's remaining lifetime (2021-2022), more features of the NanoCommons KI will become available. Therefore, it will become increasingly easy to reach the wider community and get a larger audience, and to develop an early-adopter customer base. The main aim of increasing the stakeholder engagement is to spread the NanoCommons' philosophy (and its way of working to develop and promote a set of sustainable solutions applicable to the nanosafety and materials modelling communities and beyond) in order to make NanoCommons better known and to build a critical mass of users and providers thereby making the overall offer more attractive. All this will ensure the sustainability of NanoCommons after the end of the project.

All of the activities listed below will support the implementation of the NanoCommons business concept. Furthermore, with this approach NanoCommons will reach a wider audience, attract new customers and gain additional potential revenue streams:

- Further identification of the community needs in order to further adapt and match NanoCommons offers to market needs in terms of tools and services [feeding into the revenue streams of "consultancy"].
- Continue with the process of identification and development of contacts for Industrial Case Studies [feeding into the revenue streams of "services"].
- Further development of the Case Studies, as demonstration examples of what NanoCommons is able to offer users and customers, showcasing the capabilities of the NanoCommons KI tools and services, and the added value from their integration and operation as a KI [feeding into the revenue streams of "services"].
- Perform further community building and dissemination activities, beyond the existing knowledge transfer-events, towards webinars, hackathons and training events. Organise them as joint events with other external events to reach out to a broader audience [feeding into the revenue streams of "subscriptions" to either personal users and/or organisational subscriptions].
- Expand the stakeholder community, attracting new users and customers:
 - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions - Innovative Training Networks (MSCA-ITN), addressing in particular the European Industrial Doctorate programs. NanoCommons aim is to link our training tools and opportunities to the MSCA-ITN projects, in order to promote the training of the new generation of early-stage researchers [feeding into the revenue streams of "project participation"].

- Other communities besides nanosafety, as data is generated in all research communities and all of them can profit from the NanoCommons know-how. Some “not-nano” communities are also interested in the prediction of materials’ properties. NanoCommons is already providing grouping and read-across tools for the prediction of toxicology but these grouping approach tools could be expanded to cover the predictions needed by those communities [feeding into the revenue streams of “subscriptions” to either personal users and/or organisational subscriptions].
- Reach the community via Journals publishing standards and policies: to support the inclusion of data management process across the whole data lifecycle including during publication, engagement with publishers can play a vital role. For example, if journals only accept articles with certain levels of Quality Assurance, compliance with community metadata standards and “FAIRness”, and require utilisation of data management process and workflows for published articles and associated datasets, the community will have to upgrade their practices of compiling and sharing their research results, and the tools and approaches provided by NanoCommons will represent attractive solutions. Our available solution include electronic lab notebooks, ontologies, metadata and data storage and sharing solution as part of their research. A first attempt at addressing the community of journal editors will be via *Nature Nanotechnology*⁵⁷, as they already published a recommendation about how to address the minimum reporting criteria for nano-bio research (Faria *et al.*, 2018) and a community response (Leong *et al.*, 2019) and a response from the original authors (Faria *et al.*, 2020). NanoCommons will follow up on that with community guidance for nanosafety data, denoting that NanoCommons is a public repository for nanosafety data and encouraging community use of the NanoCommons KI. Authors of recent nanosafety papers will be invited to submit the data underpinning their publications, and a nanosafety data curation prize offered to stimulate uptake and change researchers’ attitudes as a means to drive best practice in data management and openness [feeding into the revenue streams of “subscriptions” to either personal users and/or organisational subscriptions].
- Increase interaction with projects and programs identified as potential users of NanoCommons project outputs or integration activities (identified in Deliverable 10.2) in order to include their data or services/tools in the NanoCommons Knowledge Base or to interact with them through the TAs, solving their needs. Invite them to the NanoCommons online trainings/hackathons/webinars so future projects address from the very beginning the NanoCommons data management recommendations [feeding into the revenue streams of “consultancy”, “services” and shall lead to either personal users and/or organisational subscriptions].
- Increase the interaction with the new member states and candidates in order to define champions that could promote the NanoCommons project on-site. [feeding into the revenue streams of “consultancy”, “services” and shall lead to personal users and/or organisational subscriptions]
- Expand the services by including other projects/organizations into the KI. The next TA call in 2021 shall be dedicated to the integration of new services. [feeding into the revenue streams of “consultancy”, “services”]

⁵⁷ <https://www.nature.com/nnano/>

6) Conclusions

Based on the initial plan reported in deliverable D10.3, within D10.4 a first business plan is presented, to support achievement of long-term economic sustainability for a NanoCommons Organisation established to maintain the projects outputs after its EU-funded period. We note of course that as a “starting community” we are only scratching the surface of what is needed in terms of nanosafety data management and nanoinformatics solutions and that significant additional investment and development is needed. However, to maintain what has been developed, several actions have already been performed in order to structure the project work towards developing a sustainable set of tools and services and a well organised organisation through which to offer them to the community. Key elements of that organisation are the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure, the NanoCommons Knowledge Base, as well as its Consultancy and Services. It can be concluded that the project consortium has reached the development stage, to be able to reach the objective of a sustainable infrastructure by the end of the project.

Additionally, in this deliverable, a presentation of the all-round sustainability approach that NanoCommons is willing to follow looking beyond just the economic level of sustainability, by addressing some of the SDGs, and therefore also the social and environmental levels of sustainability is given. Challenges for achieving economic sustainability of tools and related products, are identified and potential options are presented. Furthermore, the actual status of the activities implemented in NanoCommons, the first NanoCommons Business Concept, and an outlook on the next steps that will be performed are shown.

Until the end of the project, the consortium aims at further promotion of the project and its future organisation, to enhance its offerings, aligned to the customers’ needs, in order to make it more attractive and therefore achieve the overall goal of a sustained infrastructure and user community. Additionally, the business plan will be refined to ensure that the nanosafety knowledge infrastructure developed by NanoCommons remains up to date, useful and widely used beyond the project lifetime.

The testing and evaluation of the NanoCommons Organisation’s Business Plan will be reported in deliverables (D10.5 and D10.6) based on the analysis and monitoring of the identified Key Exploitable Results and the further developments within the NanoCommons project.

An immediate output from D10.4 will be that NanoCommons will need to restructure its public appearance via its project website in order to show in a clearer, more user-friendly and more attractive way its core assets.

7) References

Faria M, Björnmalm M, Thurecht KJ. et al. Minimum information reporting in bio–nano experimental literature. *Nature Nanotech* 13, 777–785 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-018-0246-4>

Faria M, Björnmalm M, Crampin EJ et al. A few clarifications on MIRIBEL. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 15, 2–3 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-019-0612-x>

Leong HS, Butler KS, Brinker CJ et al. On the issue of transparency and reproducibility in nanomedicine. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 14, 629–635 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-019-0496-9>

Papadiamantis AG, Klaessig FC, Exner TE, Hofer S, Hofstaetter N, Himly M, Williams MA, Doganis P, Hoover MD, Afantitis A, Melagraki G, Nolan TS, Rumble J, Maier D, Lynch I. Metadata Stewardship in Nanosafety Research: Community-Driven Organisation of Metadata Schemas to Support FAIR Nanoscience Data. *Nanomaterials*. 2020; 10(10):2033. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10102033>

Annexes

Annex 1 – Results of the NanoCommons Online Survey

The table below shows the results of the NanoCommons online survey (December 2020), where a total of 70 participants had participated. The number of participants has not increased much since January 2019 (+12 participants) and therefore the results are quite similar. In the beginning of 2021, NanoCommons will start a new promotion campaign of the online survey in order to continuously adapt the project offerings to the community needs.

No.	Question	Response	Total	% (Dec. 2020)	% (Feb. 2020)	% (Jan. 2019)	Selected (>40%)
5	Experimental Design Service(s)	Experimental design for nanoinformatics	28	40%	42%	38%	*
		Online lab-books, data acquisition	42	60%	61%	59%	*
		Data curation templates	29	41%	43%	45%	*
		I don't know if I need it!	10	14%	12%	12%	
		None of the above	10	14%	15%	14%	
		Other (please specify)	7	10%	10%	10%	
6	Data Processing and Analysis	Data cleansing, mining and analysis	32	46%	48%	47%	*
		Modelling (statistical, mechanistic etc.)	39	56%	57%	57%	*
		ISA-TAB tools	13	19%	19%	17%	
		Ontology services	14	20%	21%	19%	
		I don't know if I need it!	21	30%	28%	29%	
		None of the above	5	7%	7%	5%	
		Other (please specify)	1	1%	1%	0%	
7	Data Visualisation and Predictive Toxicity	Omics	13	19%	19%	17%	
		Risk assessment tools	36	51%	52%	50%	*
		QSARs	19	27%	28%	26%	
		Modelling tools	40	57%	58%	57%	*
		I don't know if I need it!	13	19%	16%	16%	
		None of the above	6	9%	9%	7%	
8	Data Storage	Software development	23	33%	34%	33%	
		Tool(s) integration	29	41%	43%	40%	*
		Online data repository and accessibility	38	54%	55%	55%	*
		Data storage (hardware)	24	34%	36%	36%	
		I don't know if I need it!	19	27%	25%	22%	
		None of the above	3	4%	4%	5%	
		Other (please specify)	0	0%	0%	0%	
9	Using DMP/Tools/QA for the data generated in the project	Currently using some form of DM or QA plans	13	19%	19%	19%	
10	FAIR Principles	Aware of FAIR principles	31	44%	42%	43%	*
		Interested in learning more about FAIR	41	59%	61%	43%	*
12	To be contacted by NanoCommons in the future	Interested	49	70%	73%	72%	*

Annex 2 – List of Services & Tools provided by the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure

The table below shows an overview of the services and tools provided by NanoCommons as of November 2020, available as TAs in the NanoCommons Knowledge Infrastructure⁵⁸, ordered by category and by the NanoCommons expert partner who provides them.

Service Provider	Category 1 (Experimental Workflows & Implementation)	Category 2 (Data Processing & Analysis)	Category 3 (Data Visualization & Predictive Toxicity)	Category 4 (Data Storage & Accessibility)
UoB	Data & Metadata Curation Semantic Annotation Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) ENM Physicochemical Characterization Experimental Workflows	Rietveld refinement of diffraction data for crystalline materials Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) Semantic Annotation Komenti AberOWL	Rietveld refinement of diffraction data for crystalline materials	Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) Semantic Annotation Data & Metadata Curation
EwC				EdelweissData ACEnano Knowledge Infrastructure
UKCEH	EcoToxicological Laboratory Workflows			
NTUA		Nanolmage TEM Image Analysis Tool Jaqpot 4 Computational Platform for In Silico Modelling Jaqpot 5 Computational Platform for In Silico Modelling	toxFlow	

⁵⁸ <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/services/>

UCD		Evaluation of Theoretical Descriptors for NM	Evaluation of Theoretical Descriptors for NM	
LEITAT	Nano-related Experimental Workflows	GUIDEnano Tool	GUIDEnano Tool	
BfR				
NovaM	Enalos Cloud Nanoinformatics Platform: A Safe-by-Design Tool for Functionalised Nanomaterials	<p>NanoXtract: Nanoparticles Image Analysis Tool Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform</p> <p>Enalos Read Across Platform: Zeta Potential Predictive Model Based on Image Nanodescriptors</p> <p>Enalos Cloud Platform: A friendly user interface for Chem / Nano Informatics Applications</p> <p>Enalos Knime data retrieving workflow for in silico modelling</p> <p>NanoCommons Knowledgebase access within KNIME through Enalos APIs</p>	<p>NanoCommons Knowledgebase access within KNIME through Enalos APIs</p> <p>Enalos Cloud Platform: A friendly user interface for Chem / Nano Informatics Applications</p>	nanoPharos Database
Biomax		Omics Data Analysis		NanoCommons Knowledge Base
MU		Using Ontologies to Make Research Data FAIR		Using Ontologies to Make Research Data FAIR
OREGON			Nanomaterial-Biological Interactions Knowledgebase	Nanomaterial-Biological Interactions Knowledgebase

Annex 3 – NanoCommons Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The list of NanoCommons KERs (Status October 2020) is listed in the chart below:

#	Category	KERs // E.g. Name of Service	Lead Partner
1	1	EcoToxicological Laboratory Workflows	UK CEH
2	1	Enalos Cloud Nanoinformatics Platform: A Safe-by-Design Tool for Functionalised Nanomaterials	NovaM
3	1	ENM Physicochemical Characterization Experimental Workflows	UoB
4	1	Nano-related Experimental Workflows	LEITAT
5	2	AberOWL	UoB
6	2	Enalos Knime data retrieving workflow for in silico modelling	NovaM
7	2	Enalos Read Across Platform: Zeta Potential Predictive Model Based on Image Nanodescriptors	NovaM
8	2	Evaluation of Theoretical Descriptors for NM	UCD
9	2	Jaqpot 5 Computational Platform for In Silico Modelling	NTUA
10	2	Komenti	UoB
11	2	NanoImage TEM Image Analysis Tool	NTUA
12	2	NanoXtract: Nanoparticles Image Analysis Tool Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform	NovaM
13	2	Omics Data Analysis	Biomax
14	3	Evaluation of Theoretical Descriptors for NanoMaterials	UCD
15	3	toxFlow	NTUA
16	4	ACEnano Knowledge Infrastructure	EwC
17	4	EdelweissData	EwC
18	4	NanoCommons Knowledge Base	Biomax
19	1, 2, 4	Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN)	UoB
20	1, 2, 4	Semantic Annotation	UoB
21	1, 4	Data & Metadata Curation	UoB
22	2, 3	Enalos Cloud Platform: A friendly user interface for Chem / Nano Informatics Applications	NovaM
23	2, 3	Guidenano Tool	LEITAT
24	2, 3	NanoCommons Knowledgebase access within KNIME through Enalos APIs	NovaM
25	2, 3	Rietveld refinement of diffraction data for crystalline materials	UoB
26	3, 4	Nanomaterial-Biological Interactions Knowledgebase	OREGON
27		Corona Analysis	UCD
28	4	Data governance (DTA template, governance process for embargoed data)	Biomax
29	4	Natural language descriptor - Ontology mapping user interface	Biomax
30	4	Bring Your Own Open Data: Making Nanosafety more FAIR	MU
31	2	Pathway analysis of omics data	MU
32		Industrial Case Studies making use of selection of tools (1-33) captured as articles (in addition to project reporting)	EwC & UoB
33	3	Apellis	NTUA